

THE SYSTEMIC NATURE OF LEXICS AND IDEOGRAPHIC DICTIONARIES

Linguistics

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Abstract

The systematic study of linguistic phenomena in the linguistic field, the specificity of the substance of the language, and the gradual separation of language and speech create a great opportunity for further research. The growing importance of ideological dictionaries that have become popular in world linguistics and social life necessitates lexical-semiological research on the basis of comprehensive, detailed and logical logic for each linguistic micro system. Because new scientific technology is the best and most effective tool for creating such dictionaries, which requires clarity of lexical-semiological research.

Looking at language as a system of systems, consistent differentiation of its phenomena, interdependence, and consistent researches and investigations began in the Uzbek linguistics in the 1970 years and 1980 years. Our modern linguistics is gradually shifting from the lexicon systemic system to the step-by-step systematic methodology and results of the systematic lexicon of the Uzbek lexicology, based on scientific, important tasks. Uzbek linguistics system lexicology and semaseology put new goals and tasks. It also requires a proper and accurate assessment of the basic unit of the language, the nature of the text, the nature and the structure, the role and position of the system in which it relates, and the linguistic and extra linguistic signs.

Today, the lexicon is regarded as an integral part of the language, its lexema, its constituent components and systemic associations: dictionary colonies and linguistic micro systems, linguistic-spiritual groups and rows, and the characteristic of each of them is becoming more relevant. There is a growing need for step-by-step analysis of the structure and structure of the organizers, consistent, and consistent with the way in which the linguistic possibilities are uttered. Linguistic micro systems make the task of identifying the center and its surroundings, their role and location, and providing scientific conclusions.

The lexical level of language is a complex and multifarious, small system (micro system), such as itself, as a whole, consisting of internal systems. Lexicon has been studied differently in various ways. Looking at the research conducted in the Uzbek lexicology of the 1990 years, it is possible to witness the systematic analysis of the linguistic units of different categories. However, there are many linguistic unions and systems that are poorly studied in the lexical language of the Uzbek language or have not been fully tested by system analysis.

The system of lexemes, which is the source of the study, is not based on the substance approach of the relief micro system. That is, the system of releases that represent the relief in the

Uzbek linguistics system is not a special source of research. This is the reason for drawing attention to the issue of releases in the Uzbek language and the system they are organizing.

In the lexical system of the Uzbek language, the relief horses, representing the subterranean appearance of the lexemes commonly formulated in terms of their specific meaning and function, form a separate microsystem. It is important for lexicographical practice to carry out the tasks of the lexemes system in the above-mentioned aspect, to define their position on the lexical layer, to identify lexical-semantic relationships based on the semantic structure of the lexems, and to reflect them in ideological dictionaries.

In the 60-70th years of the XX century, attention was paid to the study of the Uzbek lexicology by topic group [1; 2]. However, in these studies, there were separate opinions on the specific subject groups of the lexica, and there was no separate study of the relationship between lexical micro groups, as well as the disclosure of linguistic and linguistic relationships of lexical units. In recent years in the field of Uzbek linguistics, particularly in the field of Uzbek lexicology, effective research has been done to systemically study the lexical language of our language, and significant achievements have been achieved. Systematic investigation of the lexical system of the Uzbek language, and, in addition, the systematic research in the systemic linguistics lexicology, as well as the resulting systematic research methods, I.Kuchkartaev, S.Giyasov, Sh.Rahmatullaev, E.Begmatov, H.Nematov, R.Rasulov, O.Bozorov, Sh.Iskandarova, R.Safarova, A.Sobirov, B.Mengliiev, Sh.Orifjonova, R.Salaev, B.Juraev, H.Saidova, B.Kilichev, G.Nematova, And Z.Yunusova [3, p. 17-20; 4, p. 35-40]. Implementation of such lexical-semiological studies has further strengthened the whole systemic problem of the Uzbek lexicology and created the basis for further research.

Each period science introduces new goals and tasks to itself, suggests solutions to problems and issues in the field [5, p. 28]. The linguistics of the XX century has also made great strides in research, with deep knowledge of the source of development and development. In the Uzbek linguistics, a number of scientific studies have been done to study the language systematically, systematically study the language and its levels, and the methodology and methods of research have been created [4, p. 35-40; 5, p. 28; 6].

The systematic nature of its laws, as it is based on the principle of the integrity of the whole, and its application to the problem of integrity of the whole language, is not equal to the sum of the pieces. Thus, the language should be regarded not as the sum of its layers, but rather as the sum of its constituencies. "Because language is systematic, its constituents are systemic" [7, p. 7]. In addition, layers that ensure linguistic integrity also have separate systems within the system and have specific learning, research methods and rules. "As the properties of straight lines are different from their triangle, language, as a system, is a whole different from its own layers, its laws and research methods differ from the features of phonological, lexical, morphological, semantic and methodological levels as well as the learning ethics" is correctly stated [7, p. 7]. In this regard, it

can be said that the systematic study of the language as part of its constituent parts is not exactly the case, because each case is based on individual premises and laws.

"It is a well-established fact that the lens system is a system, the language is also system, the system of linguistic systems, that is, the linguistic system. This is particularly evident in the vocabulary and lexicon of the language" [8, p. 101] The language began to be more advanced than the systematic study of its layers on the lexicon. The lexical layer is the center of the language, as it is centered [9, p. 25-27]. Therefore, systematic study of language phenomena in the 1970 years of the last century was carried out on the dictionary composition of the language. The initial research on the systematic study of the Lexicology can be attributed to the names of I.Kuchkartaev, Sh.Rahmatullaev, I.Abdurahmanov, R.Yunusov and other linguists.

At present, all the levels of Uzbek linguistics have been summarized as a result of generalization of phenomena, thereby establishing the essence of the linguistic substance. At the same time, Uzbek systemic lexicology and semasiology have made remarkable achievements [10]. The results of the lexics study of the Uzbek linguistics system were summarized, and the Uzbek language was fully founded in the lexicology of the system [4, p. 35-40].

We will continue to search for answers to the question of how our observations will be clarified directly by the systemic nature of the lexical surface, given the focus of the focus on the lexicon system and its subject matter.

"Because objective world is a system, the linguistic expression of this system, reflected in the mind, is also systematic. Language is multifaceted in terms of ontological (internal) structure, with each level being systematic. In particular, the lexical plane is a system consisting of the relation of certain lexical semantic groups, reflecting the dialectics of the whole and the fragment, the dialectic" [11, p. 7].

Hypo-hyperconimic relationships that hold the systemic system of the language are an important basis for ensuring the inner integrity of the system, the strict stratum of the joints and the interstitial connections. Hence, it should be noted that the language's system is based on the hierarchical structure of the hyponymy relation and, of course, this attitude is relative. The concept of hypo-hyperonimic attitude and the fact that it is within the system is relatively extensively studied in Uzbek linguistics [12]. The hypoheperonimic response to the lexical-semantic version of the lexeme, which is the unit of the lexical layer, can be traced by the above-mentioned lexical-semasiological research.

We believe that the systematic study of the lexical level of the Uzbek language is enough to justify our opinion. In particular, "degeneration" (O.Bozorov), "personality" micro space (Sh.Iskandarova), "hyponimia" (R.Safarova), semantic structure of person names (M.Narzieva), linguistic graduonimia (Sh.Orifjonova), partonimia (N. Nishonova), zoonym (H.Saidova), systemic of lexical layer (A.Sobirov), system analysis of field lexics (M.Abdiev, B.Kilichev),

“plant” archiseme (G.Nematova), the lexemes with archiseme “animal” (N.Nishanova) is remarkable [13].

It (mind) will be copied from the right moment and it will be part. These parts are sorted, grouped and classified on the basis of similarities or differences in their particular relationships. The concept of perceptions is expressed through language and their classification. While interpreting and interpreting languages are interrelated, different linguistic societies, as well as experts in every field, focus on the crucial aspects of the multifaceted nature phenomenon and prioritize these aspects in the classification process. This is related to the source and subject matter of the study. When we draw attention to the above-mentioned statements, we find that the first is a purely philological nature, the second is a conjunction, and the third is terminological interpretations. The most important of them is the interpretation of the “Dictionary of the Uzbek Language”. Different aspects of the words, which are the source of research, can be of different importance, depending on what methods are used in linguistic interpretations.

As you know, the language is a very diverse socio-psychological phenomenon, a process. Each of these edges can be subject to a separate subject matter. For this reason, throughout the whole history of linguistics, such as linguistics, such as comparativism, naturalism, diachronic (historical) linguistics, synchronic linguistics, structuralism, statistical linguistics, psycholinguistics, sociology, logical linguistics, linguistic typology, practical linguistics, phonetics, phonology, lexicology, lexicography, morphemics, grammar, derivation, semantics, specializing in the study of different levels of language and others are living side by side.

Linguistics departments specialize in studying different languages (large) units if the flow of texts serves in depth study of some aspects of the multilingual language taken as a whole. All the linguistic trends and trends constantly fill us with knowledge of the main source of our knowledge – knowledge of the language (in some cases, even though the rule of one aspect of the same thing denied the conclusions of the second). For this reason, linguistic research is different from the source of the study and the subject matter of the study.

The language is a complicated and multifaceted phenomenon, and its constituents are a relative independent integral within their system that has such a complex structure and nature, based on mutual relations.

On the basis of the researches conducted, it can be said that each division must be based on the relationships of individual groups, system associations, their internal relations, and their generality and uniqueness, based on their relationship with other commonalities [14]. In contrast to the contemporary linguistics, in terms of substance analysis, it is desirable to determine the substance of linguistic associations and their units through interrelated relationships that are interconnected. Indeed, when analyzing the sources of the system, the systemologist is able to

disclose the systematic nature of the observable phenomenon, not by summarizing the peculiarities of the character, but by combining similar events.

In today's Uzbek lexicology, which has raised the level of systematic nature of language lexicon to the level of complexity of linguistic phenomena such as interconnectedness and legality of systemic associations (LMG, LMS, LMT), as well as the systematic nature of the lexical layer, defining the status, structure, composition of lexeme, linguistic, linguistic and spiritual relationships. Systematic research methods have been developed to accomplish these tasks, and the results of the research have been summarized. It has been noted that a number of scientific studies have been conducted to determine the content of the dictionary, thematic study, and the composition of the lexical areas. This, in turn, plays an important practical role in making a worthy contribution to the development of our lexicography.

Today it is necessary to recognize that the results of the lexico-semiological research, which is a new stage of glossary and a new generation of dictionaries – Ideological, thesaurus dictionaries and the basis for their creation, have a priority.

The systematic lexical leveling of the language, identifying system microcircuits (LMG, LSG), defining their position in the lexical system, and the need to clarify the interdisciplinary lexical-semantic relationships put the subject matter of the linguistic system up-to-date. Hence, the definition of the social status of a particular language, its scientific focus on the lexical layer is closely linked to its fluidity and practice. The effectiveness and the scientific significance of lexical-semasiological research is a solid foundation and factor for the perfect linguistic practice.

We note that the lexicology and lexicography are closely interconnected, and this is based on the fact that the linguistic unity and its linguistic essence are the subject of social function. As the lexicographer has a rich experience, his theory as a science develops and improves. Diversity of dictionary requirements, diversity of dictionary types, and social need for them require a serious approach to this area and a separate study.

Uzbek dictionaries study is also one of the most profound areas of its history. Till M.Koshghariy (“Devoni lug’at-at turk”) are in the process of creating modern dictionaries that will help to modernize the modern linguistic competence capable of responding to modern requirements. Specifically, our focus is on creating ideological (thematic, thesaurus) dictionaries that are viewed as a new and effective example in the field of translation, and their broad introduction into practice. There are valuable comments that the world and the Russian linguistics will give a great deal of positive results in the study of the various components of the language in the context of ideological (unifying to specific groups) context. Specifically, authors of the “Russian-Uzbek Thematic Glossary” say that such a method yields great results [15, p. 519].

It is known that the study of the lexical level of the language on the basis of thematic groups and squares, based on the specific association, community and similarity of the language units, is of particular practical outcomes. Thus, the main purpose of the lexicon in the ideological (thematic) context is to integrate the various (linguistic, terminological, literary) meanings of the word, to analyze, to study and to apply them properly.

Thus, the study of the lexical level of the language, the systematic theme of the language, from the semantic point of view, is the basis of the ideological analysis. Ideologically studying the linguistic units serves to get a complete and comprehensive knowledge of them.

Some of the lexicology studies are based on this point of view and the idea that ideological analysis in Uzbek language can be the basis for creating ideological dictionaries. Because in the subsequent lexico-semasiological studies [11, p.7], systematic analysis of words is closely related to the spiritual proximity of the words, which serves as the main material for the creation of ideological dictionaries based on the principle of union on the basis of spirituality. As we have noted in our Linguistics: “If the lexical meaning is interpreted using examples collected on a particular system, the value of this dictionary is high. This is because of the objective picture of the vocabulary in such work” [16, p. 399].

Looking back on the history of the lexicography, examples of ideological dictionary based on ideological analysis can be found in the world linguistics, as well as Russian lexicography. The English, French, German, Spanish dictionaries have a lot of dictionaries. The work of lexicographers such as K.Plotts, K.Babov, A.Vrgulev, L.Rozkovsova, Z.Ganusova and G.Fogt is of particular importance. “The dictionary (the ideological dictionary), which gives an idea of the essence of the word with all its essence and system, creates conditions for easy and easy access to a particular language. Therefore, this is one of the essential dictionaries. This dictionary is the treasure of the language” [17, p. 26].

The rising value of ideological dictionaries, which is the “treasure” of the broader lexis in world linguistics and social life, requires research and research in the field of lexicography to be based on a profound, scientific basis for every linguistic micro system. Indeed, as noted above, certain lexical-semasiological research results should serve as an important material for modern dictionaries. “We define explicitly explicitly dictionaries of strong semantic relationships among all its constituent units as “thesaurus” [18, p. 365]. From this point of view, the importance of systematic verification of the separate linguistic-spiritual group of reliefs is obvious. Lexical units of the system and their system integrity is one of the important tasks facing the modern linguistics.

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